

Jute Seeds—*Corchorus Capsularis*. Part II.*

The Composition of Oil *Corchorus*.

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The object of this investigation was to determine the constituents of a specimen of jute-seed oil, in addition to making a study of the chemical composition of the seeds.

A large sample of jute seeds (*Corchorus capsularis*) was received from the Monipur Agricultural Farm, Dacca. They were dried, powdered and extracted with light petroleum ether in a large copper Soxhlet's apparatus and the oil obtained from the extract was used for the investigation, the results of which are given below.

Partial analysis of the crude oil was made by the author in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 205). It has been recently reported that the oil is now being largely used with highly satisfactory results by the natives of Hill Tippera, Bengal, as a specific for skin diseases (N. C. Chowdhury, "Jute in Bengal," p. 48). In Hill Tippera, the oil is extracted by the following crude process. "The seed is at first pounded and then moistened with water. This paste is put into a vessel with perforated bottom. Another vessel is placed beneath it to collect the oil dropped down. A third vessel or earthen pot with ignited charcoal within is kept over the first vessel, containing the paste. The heat is continued until the oil is fully extracted" (cf. Chowdhury, *loc. cit.*). The yield is reported to be one seer of the oil from 5 seers of the seed—i.e., 20 per cent. of the seeds, but a sample of the seeds, used by the author, gave only 14.73 per cent. of the oil on extracting with light petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°).

Physical and Chemical Examination of the Oil.

The petroleum extract of the seeds was a yellowish brown oil. The last trace of petroleum ether was removed by heating in a vacuum. On standing the oil deposited a small amount of solid, forming a dry adherent film on glass at the ordinary temperature. The oil burnt with a bright, odourless, almost non-sooty flame on a wick of 4 mm. thickness and the length of the flame was 45 mm. There was no deposition of crust and the consumption was 6 grams per hour. The oil did not give any colour reaction with saudouin

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and Halphen tests. Preliminary test showed the possible presence of archidic and lignoceric acids in the oil by the flocculent precipitate of the soap solution in 90 per cent. alcohol at the ordinary temperature (Holde, "Hydrocarbon Oils and Saponifiable Fats and Waxes," p 388). The oil became rancid on standing in air.

Attempts to refine the oil by treatment with a solution of caustic soda was found useless on account of the difficulty met with in breaking the emulsion when once formed. For experimental purpose, the following method of refining was adopted, which gave satisfactory results:—A lot of 100 grams of the oil was well ground up in a dish with 50 grams of solid anhydrous sodium carbonate and 50 c.c. of water. The mass was then dried on the water-bath and the residue was again stirred up with coarsely powdered pumice stone, previously saturated with a 10 per cent. solution of caustic soda and ignited. The whole mass was then exhausted in a Soxhlet's apparatus with dry ether, the ether evaporated off and the oil heated in a current of carbon dioxide at 110°. 80.5 Grams of a light yellow oil with an acid value of 1.5 were obtained. Attempts to bleach the oil by Fuller's earth and bone charcoal were unsuccessful. The refined oil was used for determining its constants and composition. A few constants of the crude oil were determined by the author (*loc. cit.*) and the values are given in Table I together with those obtained for the refined oil.

TABLE I.

			Refined oil.	Crude oil.
Specific gravity at 28°	0.923	0.921
Refractive index	1.4615 at 29.7°	1.4705 at 30.1°
Solidifying point	-20°	—
Iodine value	102.6 (Habl's)	109.2 (Wij's)
Saponification value	184.6	184.4
Acid value	1.5	24.07
Acetyl value	27.3	—
Reichert-Meissel value	0.16	—
Unsaponifiable matter % (Spitz and Hönig)	2.25	3.0
Soluble acids (% of butyric acid)	0.32	—
Insoluble acid % (Hafelmann and Steiner)	94.1	—
Glycerol %	9.2	—

The iodine value would indicate a semi-drying oil. The drying power of the oil was determined by spreading it over a glass plate 5 cm. by 10 cm. at ordinary temperature but only a trace of film was developed on the glass plate after a fortnight. The low Reichert-Meissel number showed that only a trace of glycerides of lower fatty acids was present while the high acetyl value indicated large amount of glycerides of the hydroxy acid.

Hydrolysis of the oil.

For a complete examination of the oil, 300 grams were employed. It was first subjected to distillation with steam but the distillate contained no volatile oil. The oil after separating from water, was hydrolysed by heating with alcoholic potash and benzol and the unsaponifiable matter was removed with naphtha by the gravimetric method of Spitz and Hönig. After evaporating off the alcohol from the soap solution, the residue was dissolved in a little water and decomposed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid in the presence of petroleum ether in a separating funnel. The acid layer was run off and the resulting fatty acid solution was washed with concentrated solution of Glauber's salt and twice with distilled water till the wash-water did not turn methyl orange red. The petroleum ether was dried for a short time with calcium chloride, filtered and distilled and the residual fatty acids were dried. A small quantity of insoluble oxy-acids separated between the acid and the petroleum ether solutions. This was filtered, well washed with petroleum ether, dissolved in warm alcohol, dried at 105° after evaporation of the alcohol and weighed. This amounted to 1.6 per cent. of the oil used.

The fatty acids.

The insoluble fatty acids were then separated into saturated and unsaturated acids by (i) the lead-salt-ether method and by (ii) Twitchell's lead-alcohol method (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

Table II gives the percentage of the saturated and the unsaturated acids as estimated by the two methods.

TABLE II.

		Unsaturated acids.	Saturated acids.
Lead-salt-ether method	...	76.89%	23.1%
Lead-alcohol method	...	80.2	19.6

The saturated acids obtained by method (ii) were practically free from unsaturated acids as the iodine value determined by Hubl's method was found to be 2.1 and after crystallisation from alcohol; the iodine value was 1.8 as compared with a value of 19.03 for the saturated acids obtained by method (i).

Table III gives the analytical constants of the insoluble acids as well as the saturated and unsaturated acids. The molecular weight of the unsaturated acids was obtained by heating the acids with an excess of alkali and then titrating the excess. The usual method of direct titration gave result much higher (300.2).

TABLE III.

	Insoluble acids.	Saturated acids.	Unsaturated acids.
Melting point	31.5°-32.7°	50°-52°	—
Refractive index at 29.7°	1.4565	—	—
Titer (solidifying point).	29.9°	—	-6°
Iodine value (Hubl's)	114.51	2.1	141.45
Saponification value	200.2	216.7	196.4
Mean molecular weight	280.2	258.9	285.6

Unsaturated Acids.

In order to ascertain the nature of the constituents of the unsaturated acids a portion of the unsaturated acids (30 grams) was oxidised in alkaline solution with 1½ per cent. solution of potassium permanganate at the ordinary temperature with constant stirring. At the end of operation, sulphurous acid was added to the mixture until all the manganese oxide had dissolved. A pure white precipitate was then obtained which was separated by filtration and treated with naphtha (b.p. under 50°) and the undissolved acids were digested with a large quantity of ether at the ordinary temperature. The ethereal solution, after the removal of the solvent, yielded the product which when crystallised from 96 per cent. alcohol separated in beautiful hexagonal plates melting at 135°. (0.2130 neutralised 6.7 c.c. of N/10 caustic potash. Neutralisation value=176.05. $C_{18}H_{36}O_4$ requires 177.6). This substance was evidently

dihydroxy-stearic acid and its formation proved the presence of oleic acid in the mixture of liquid acids. The portion of the oxidation product remaining undissolved by the above described treatment with ether was repeatedly boiled with large quantities of water and the liquid filtered. The filtrate yielded a crystalline deposit melting at 165° which, after crystallisation from alcohol, separated in small thin needles melting at the same temperature (0.1344 neutralised 3.85 c.c. of N/10 caustic potash. Neutralisation value 160.4 ; $C_{18}H_{36}O_6$ requires 161.2). This substance was thus identified to be tetrahydroxy-stearic acid (sativic acid) and its formation proved the presence of linolic acid in the oil. As no hexahydroxy-stearic acid could be isolated from the product of oxidation it may be concluded that linolenic acid is not a constituent of the oil.

As the foregoing method is not a quantitative one and is only useful to prove the presence of oleic acid in the unsaturated acids, the quantity of their constituents was determined by means of their bromine addition products as recommended by Jamieson and Baughmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1198). Accordingly, the unsaturated acid prepared according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthalor (Lewkowitch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes," 6th edition, Vol. I, p. 585) were dissolved in dry ether and the mixture cooled to -10° ; bromine was added slowly drop by drop. During the addition of bromine, the temperature was not allowed to rise above -5° and the mixture was allowed to stand for two hours at about -10° . No precipitate insoluble in ether was obtained. The excess of bromine was then removed from the ethereal solution by washing in a separating funnel with an aqueous solution of sodium thiosulphate. The ethereal solution was then dried by anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. The ether was removed by distillation and the residue was dissolved in hot petroleum ether. After standing in an ice-chest overnight, the insoluble tetrabromide was filtered through a weighed Gooch crucible. The filtrate was concentrated to less than half of its original volume and again cooled and allowed to stand as before. After filtering this crop of tetrabromide crystals, the filtrate was evaporated to a volume of 35 c.c. and allowed to stand in the ice-chest overnight when no more crystals separated. Each crop of crystals was found to melt at 113° - 114° , the melting point for tetrabromo-linolic acid. Finally all of the petroleum ether was removed and the residue weighed. The bromine content of the residue was then determined.

The data of the analysis of the bromo-derivatives are given below:—

	Gm.
Sample of unsaturated acids	3·5806
Linolic tetrabromide insoluble in petroleum ether, m.p. 113°-114°	2·7151
Residue (dibromide and tetrabromide)	3·8960
Bromine content of residue	41·954%
Dibromide in the residue 66·33% or	2·5842
Tetrabromide in residue 33·67% or	1·3118
Total tetrabromide found	4·0269
Linolic acid equivalent to tetrabromide 1·879 g. or	52·48%
Oleic acid equivalent to dibromide 1·6437 g. or	46·05%

That the tetrabromide was still present in the residue was proved by the fact that methyl alcohol extracted a further quantity of tetrabromide melting at 112°.

The percentage of linolic and oleic acids in the unsaturated acids were converted into the percentage of glycerides in the original oil as follows:—

	Found.	Calculated on basis of 100 %.	Original oil.	Glycerides in original oil.
Oleic acid	46·05%	46·76%	37·50%	39·18%
Linolic acid	52·48	53·24	42·70	44·63
Total	98·53	100·00	80·20	83·81

The theoretical iodine value of a mixture consisting of 46·76 per cent. oleic acid and 53·24 per cent. linolic acid is 138·67 which fairly agrees with the observed iodine value of the unsaturated acids (141·45).

Saturated Acids.

Attempted separation of higher saturated acids by recrystallisation from alcohol.—The solid fatty acids separated by Twitchell's method were fractionally crystallised from 90 per cent alcohol at 15° when the least soluble fraction on further crystallisation melted at 70°-71°. It was thus evident that some acid of higher carbon content than stearic acid was present and the substance on further crystallisation melted at 74°-75°. (0·2112 g. neutralised 5·7 c.c. of N/10

caustic potash. Neutralisation value=151.13). The product evidently consists of a mixture of archidic and lignoceric acids, the latter predominating. In order to ascertain the quantity of the "crude archidic acid," Renard test (*Compt. rend.*, 1871, 73, 1330) for archidic acid was applied to the oil. Accordingly the fatty acids from 16.66 gms. of the oil were dissolved in 100 c.c. of 90 per cent. alcohol and precipitated by adding 1.6 grams of lead acetate in 50 c.c. of 90 per cent. alcohol. After standing overnight the separated lead salts were decomposed by 5 per cent. hydrochloric acid and the solid acids thus obtained were dissolved in 100 c.c. of 90 per cent. alcohol by warming and then cooled for thirty minutes in ice-water at 15°. The crystals were separated by suction and washed three times with 90 per cent. alcohol cooled at 15°. Finally the crystals were thoroughly washed with 70 per cent. alcohol until the washings remained clear on adding water. The filtrate and washings were measured. The crystals were then dissolved in absolute alcohol and weighed after drying at 100°. The correction for the amount in solution was then added to the amount found. The total yield was found to be 0.2825 gm. (corr.), which melted at 71° (capillary tube method) and the percentage of the "crude archidic acid" was found to be 1.69 in the oil.

The fatty acids obtained after evaporating off the alcohol from the mother-liquor of the "crude archidic acid" were fractionally crystallised from 75 per cent. alcohol and the fractions representing the two extremes of solubility, which melted at 57°-59° and 53°-55.5° respectively, were analysed with the following results:

I. Fraction melting at 57°-59°.

0.2812 neutralised 10.16 c.c. of N/10 caustic potash.

Neutralisation value=202.3

II. Fraction melting at 53°-55.5°.

0.2006 neutralised 7.15 c.c. of N/10 caustic potash.

Neutralisation value=199.6.

These results showed that both of the above fractions consisted of a mixture of palmitic and stearic acids.

It was however found that the composition of the mixture was unchanged on re-crystallisation from alcohol and thus acted as a chemical entity. It was therefore not possible to separate such acids by fractional crystallisation and the compounds with their constant melting point and molecular weight would appear as chemical entities by the usual purity criteria.

In view of these facts it was thought advisable to separate the saturated fatty acid constituents of jute seed oil by the distillation of their methyl ester in vacuum and a sufficient quantity of the material is now being prepared for further analytical work which will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

Unsaponifiable Matter.

A portion of the unsaponifiable matter prepared by the method of Spitz and Hönig when dissolved in alcohol and the solution concentrated deposited beautiful crystals after standing overnight which after crystallisation from 90 per cent. alcohol was obtained in long thin lamina.

The melting point was not sharp, at 114° it softened and at 126° it was liquified and on twice crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 128°. It was optically active and was precipitated by digitonin and gave the characteristic Liebermann-Burchard colour reaction for a phytosterol. The air dried digitonide from the unsaponifiable matter was powdered and extracted with ether, then the digitonin separated by heating with acetic anhydride for 30 minutes. The separated acetates crystallised from alcohol and melted at 128°-129.5°. Evidently it showed that it was not a single substance but formed mixed crystals of sterols.

The percentage of sterol was determined by the digitonide method of Windaus. The unsaponifiable matter from 20.21 gms. of the oil was warmed with 25 c.c. of 95 per cent alcohol and mixed with 25 c. c. of hot 1 per cent. solution of digitonin in 96 per cent. alcohol. After standing overnight the precipitate was filtered on a weighed Gooch crucible, washed successively with alcohol and ether, dried at 110° and weighed. The sterol amounted to 0.6145 per cent. in the oil. The unsaponifiable matter had an iodine value of 62.15 and the alcoholic mother-liquor left after the separation of sterol by crystallisation yielded on evaporation a small quantity of yellow resinous substance having a characteristic smell. When boiled with acetic anhydride it dissolved completely and on cooling the lower layer of the solution was clear but a magma of crystals separated out on the top of the liquid thus indicating the propable presence of some higher alcohol of aliphatic series. On account of the very small amount of the material it could not be further examined.

Summary.

The chemical and physical characteristics of a sample of extracted jute seed oil have been determined. A study has been made of the composition of the oil, the results of which are given below:—

Glycerides of oleic acid	...	39.18 per cent.
„ „ linolic acid	...	44.63

The oil contains a small quantity of "crude archidic acid" (0.169 per cent.) and palmitic and stearic acids. From the unsaponifiable portion of the oil a very small amount of a phytosterol was obtained. When purified, the oil is suitable as a food and is also satisfactory for burning purpose.

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